

Impact of Rajyoga Lifestyle of Brahma Kumaris on Spiritual Happiness Among The Educated Youth

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DoI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20574271>

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Citation:

Bithindranath Bhaumik, Dr. Rajesh Arora(2026). Impact of Rajyoga Lifestyle of Brahma Kumarison Spiritual Happiness Among The Educated Youth. International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Transactions, 8(5), 24–32. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20574271>

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Accepted: 23 May 2026

Available online: 06 June 2026

Abstract

Human-denying science has pushed material development to its pinnacle. The perception of male and female, due to physical consciousness, has rendered humans mentally ill, a condition beyond repression. Stress and mental fatigue are increasing day by day among educated youth. In the present modern society, where science has provided every comfort and convenience through rapid technological progress, however, due to economic pressures in the lives of educated youth, social and family problems have become complicated leading to stress and ultimately suicide. The search for happiness, peace, tranquility and well-being has become a significant topic in the minds of young people. Among the various ways to achieve spiritual happiness, the teachings of the Brahma Kumaris—a global spiritual organization founded in India in 1936—encourage stress management, inner peace, and personal growth through Raja Yoga meditation, emotional control, mindfulness, self-awareness, and spiritual education.

This paper explores how the teachings of the Brahma Kumaris can contribute to the attainment of spiritual happiness for educated youth, assessing their mental, physical, familial, and social well-being. Using a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods, the